

Balancing Act: Unravelling the Impact of Maternal Employment on Development of College Going Students

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Abstract This research paper, titled "Balancing Act: Unravelling the Impact of Maternal Employment on Development of College going students" investigates the complex relationship between maternal employment and various aspects of adolescent development.

The study aims to contribute to existing literature by exploring both positive and negative impacts, shedding light on the intricate dynamics that characterize this familial balancing act. Drawing on psychological and sociological theories, the research addresses critical gaps in understanding how maternal employment influences Some personality traits such as Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Openness to Experiences (attachment, family dynamics, and socio-economic factors) in the context of adolescent growth. Employing a randomise sampling methodology, the study employs Survey method for data acquisition. Key variables, including maternal employment and adolescent development, are defined and measured, and statistical analysis are applied to unravel the intricacies of this relationship. The results offer valuable insights into the multifaceted impact of maternal employment on adolescents, providing implications for future research and policy considerations. This study contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding work-family balance and its implications for the well-being of the adolescent population.

Keywords: Adolescent, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Extraversion, Maternal employment, Openness to Experiences

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence emerges as a pivotal juncture in our lives, often analogized to a burst of energy reminiscent of the vibrancy of spring, acknowledged as a paramount period, it represents the pinnacle of excitement and vitality. What renders it noteworthy is the substantial research emphasis uniquely dedicated to this stage, surpassing the collective attention given to all other life phases. Scholars persistently delve into adolescence, unveiling novel perspectives. This perpetual commitment mirrors an ongoing effort to grasp and address the distinct challenges faced by teenagers.

According to Hurlock in 1973, adolescence is split into three periods:

Pre-adolescence (10-12 years old),

Early adolescence (13-16 years old),

Late adolescence (17-21 years old).

Entering late adolescence is like stepping into a time of significant personal, physical, psychological and academic growth. This phase often aligns with going to college, where individuals experience increased independence and self-discovery. As late adolescents become college students, they work on figuring out who they are, forming connections with others, and developing skills for their future careers. Academic establishments become a lively environment for exploration, helping shape perspectives, build resilience, and embrace the responsibilities that come with becoming an adult. Late adolescence and the college experience together play a big role in shaping individuals in important ways.

Big Five Model of Personality: The OCEAN model is highly utilized and well-regarded in the context of behavioral and psychological research. This model incorporates distinct and relatively independent dimensions, including extraversion, emotional stability, agreeableness, openness to experience, and conscientiousness. Each factor comprises specific sub-traits that precisely delineate the characteristics of the considered factor.

A trait represents a facet of personality, embodying consistent response patterns stemming from specific experiences and forming a cohesive system. Traits, as charted by scholars such as Allport, Cattell, and Guilford (1960), offer valuable insights into how individuals behave across distinct situations. The 'trait approach' proves beneficial for characterizing individuals based on specific traits they possess.

A maternal working status can affect how college students act and think. It might make them more independent, resilient, and better at managing time. How much it affects them depends on things like when their mothers work and how involved they are in their child's life. Some studies say, it can be good, like making them more adaptable and self-reliant however some studies may beg to differ, but every individual (adolescent) is different. Scientists are still looking for into it to understand it better.

In conclusion, the link between a maternal employment and the personality traits of college students is intricate, and researchers persist in investigating this connection for a more nuanced grasp of its effects.

I.I. IMPORTANT DEFINITIONS

2.1 Agreeableness evaluates how well individuals can get along with others and their compatibility in social interactions. This trait is identified by attributes like affection, warmth, compassion, forgiveness, kindness, inherent trust, and generosity (John et al., 1994).

2.2 Conscientiousness includes qualities such as reliability, efficiency, productivity, organization, hard work, ambition, and dependability (John et al., 1994; McCrae & Costa, 1987). It measures the extent to which a person takes others into consideration when making decisions.

2.3 Emotional Stability denotes a person's aptitude for maintaining a steady and composed state. Being emotionally stable implies the capacity to remain calm amidst stressors, minimizing the occurrence of negative emotions. Consequently, individuals with emotional stability are more adept at sustaining productivity and capability when faced with life's adversities.

2.4 Extraversion is identified as "a quality characterized by a keen interest in others and external events, along with the confidence to venture into the unknown" (Ewen, 1998).

2.5 Openness to Experience is manifested in individuals who are daring, imaginative, original, and possess diverse interests. This trait signifies the extent to which people are open to adjusting their ideas and activities in response to new concepts or situations. McCrae and Costa (1987).

2.6 Maternal employment A working mother, defined by the Oxford English Dictionary, is a woman balancing paid employment with the care of her children. Conversely, a housewife, now more commonly known as a homemaker, is a woman whose primary focus lies in the management of her family's home. In the realm of maternal employment, we recognize the contemporary term "homemaker" as a more accepted description for those emphasizing their role in household management.

I.II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Investigating the effects of parental behaviour on a group of female students (N=200), Manju Sharma (2003) utilized Ohja's (1993) Parental Behaviour Inventory. The study revealed that parental behaviour plays a crucial role in shaping specific personality traits, such as ego strength and self-concept, especially among adolescent girls, as concluded by Sharma in her findings.

Liu, F., & Wang, S. (2020) Parenting style refers to a distinctive and enduring pattern of interaction established as parents educate and nurture their children. This encompasses the levels of both protective instincts and emotional warmth demonstrated by parents throughout the teaching process.

Chudhari (2017) investigated 160 only children (80 boys and 80 girls) aged 12 to 14 with working and non-working mothers. The study found that the employment status of mothers did not significantly affect the personality development or emotional competences of only children.

A study of 'Maternal Working Hours and the Well-Being of Adolescent Children' by Silvia Mendolia (2014). The evidence presented in this study implies that more hours of maternal employment do not make a teenage child more likely to have low levels of psychological well-being.

The 2022 study by Vhadage et al. underscores a significant correlation between maternal working hours and mean development scores, contributing to the ongoing discourse on the complex interplay between maternal employment and child well-being in contemporary society. However, further research and nuanced exploration of methodological aspects are crucial to comprehensively understand the implications of this relationship.

De Coster, S., & Zito, R. C. (2013) in this study research highlights the diversity within groups of homemakers and employed mothers concerning their well-being, parenting behaviours, and the depression of their adolescent children. It emphasizes that incongruence in roles and ideologies among mothers can lead to distress, influencing parenting and contributing to adolescent depression. The study emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of both homemakers and employed mothers, suggesting that considering them as homogeneous groups is overly simplistic. Further research should explore additional sources of

heterogeneity, the role of partners/spouses, and reciprocal relationships between incongruity, distress, parenting, and adolescent well-being.

Study conducted by Dhingra, Vipra, and Keswani (2019), titled 'The Influence of Working and Homemaker Mothers on Child Development,' indicates that working mothers not only address their children's financial needs but also promote self-decision making by offering less supervision. This, in turn, contributes to increased confidence in their children. The findings of the study suggest a positive correlation between these factors and the overall well-being of the child.

II.III. RATIONALE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Maternal employment is on a trajectory to persist as a lasting facet of societal dynamics, mirroring the ongoing evolution of work norms. A noticeable shift towards inclusive and flexible employment frameworks is evident, driven by a growing recognition of the vital contributions made by mothers in the workforce. This lasting change in work-life harmony, and gender equality underscores the continued relevance of maternal employment in the evolving professional landscape. In light of this, studying the impact of maternal employment on the development of college-going students is particularly pertinent in the current era. The increasing participation of mothers in the workforce necessitates a comprehensive understanding of how their employment influences the academic and personal growth of their children. This research holds significance for educators, policymakers, and parents, providing insights into the shifting dynamics of family structures and their consequences on the educational landscape. As maternal employment becomes more prevalent, unraveling its intricate connection with student development is essential for adapting educational approaches. It sheds light on the evolving roles within families and the implications for college-bound students, guiding the creation of tailored support systems and educational strategies to help them to overcome the challenges faced.

By acknowledging this unique interplay between maternal employment and students' educational journeys, we can foster a more inclusive and effective learning environment that aligns with the changing fabric of society, promoting holistic development and academic success. Initially, this research aims to uncover potential effects of maternal employment on the Personality traits of college going students. Furthermore, it seeks to pinpoint any positive impacts, such as heightened emotional stability and openness to new experience resulting from exposure to working role models. Analysing the potential influence of maternal employment on college going students subjective personality traits and overall development, it can equip policymakers and practitioners with valuable insights. This understanding can facilitate the development of more effective strategies to support working mothers and foster the healthy development of college going students.

Furthermore, the research contributes to existing literature addressing gender variations in personality traits among college going students. By comparing outcomes for male and female students with mothers in varied occupational roles—whether employed or homemakers—the study aims to discern specific gender-related impacts of maternal employment on college going students development. This information can guide efforts focused on promoting gender equality and enhancing the overall personality traits of college going students, irrespective of gender.

Moreover, the investigation has the potential to offer valuable insights into strategies for promoting gender equality and improving the personality traits of both male and female students. For instance, if the study uncovers that maternal employment adversely affects the personality traits of college going student, policymakers and educators may need to design specific intervention programmes to support this group. Conversely, should the research indicate a positive impact of maternal employment on both male and female college going students, it could inform policy decisions geared towards encouraging and supporting women's participation in the workforce.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the impact of Maternal employment on personality traits of college going students
2. To study the Gender difference on personality traits of college going students.

III. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There will be significant impact of maternal employment on personality traits of college going students.
2. There will be significant Gender difference on personality traits of college going students.

IV. VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

7.1 Independent Variable: 1. Gender (Male & Female), 2. Maternal employments (Working and Home maker)

7.2 Dependent Variable: Personality traits (Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Extraversion, Openness to new Experience)

V. RESEARCH DESIGN TO BE IMPLEMENTED

Survey method is used for data collection. Sample size 32 (Male 16 and Female 16) were randomly selected from the Pune city. Sample are of college going student in the age group of 17 to 21years old.

Inclusive criteria Both male and female college going students (Age 17 Yrs To 21 Yrs) are considered whose mother are working and homemaker.

Exclusion criteria Study has excluded mentally retarded, physically challenged and rural college going students

VI. TOOLS FOR THIS STUDY

Ten-Item Personality Inventory- Authors: S. Gosling, P. Rentfrow, W. Swann (2003), TIPI- Online version, a 10-item measure of the Big Five dimensions. Which major five personality traits (Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Extraversion, Openness to new Experience)

VII. TABLES AND FIGURES:

1. Above Average (AA) Personality traits of Adolescent (Table 1)

Traits →	Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Emotional Stability	Openness to Experiences
AA - Adolescent whose mother working	06 *	05	08 *	06 *	09
AA- Adolescent whose mother home maker	04	09 *	07	03	10 *

*Represents higher scores in the category

2. Gender wise data of adolescents whose mothers are Working (Table 2)

T.1Scores →	Below Average			Average			Above Average		
Traits ↓	F	M	Total	F	M	Total	F	M	Total
Extraversion	01	02	03	03	04	07	04	02	06
Agreeableness	01	-	01	03	07	10	04	01	05
Conscientiousness	-	-	-	01	07	08	07	01	08
Emotional Stability	01	-	01	03	06	09	04	02	06
Openness to Experiences	-	-	-	02	05	07	06	03	09
Mean							5	1.8	

3. Gender wise data of adolescents whose mothers are Home maker (Table 3)

T.2 Scores →	Below Average			Average			Above Average		
Traits ↓	F	M	Total	F	M	Total	F	M	Total
Extraversion	02	01	03	04	05	09	02	02	04

Agreeableness	-	-	-	02	05	07	06	03	09
Conscientiousness	-	02	02	03	04	07	05	02	07
Emotional Stability	01	01	02	05	06	11	02	01	03
Openness to Experiences	-	01	01	03	02	05	05	05	10
Mean							4	2.6	

VIII. ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table 1 depicts the results of the survey conducted among adolescents of working and non-working mothers. The adolescents who are surveyed as per the earlier mentioned tables and the data is tabulated as above. 32 Adolescents, are divided into 16 working mother's adolescent and 16 of home maker mother's adolescent. During this study, the 06 adolescent are found to be above average on Extraversion trait whose mothers are working and 04 adolescent were found above average whose mother are home maker. However, a total 05 adolescent were found to be above average on Agreeableness trait whose mothers are working and 09 adolescent were found above average whose mothers are home maker. The total 08 adolescents were found to be above average on Conscientiousness trait whose mothers are working and 07 adolescent were found above average whose mothers are home maker, 06 adolescent were found to be above average on Emotional Stability trait whose mothers are working and 03 adolescent were found above average whose mothers are home maker. During study, a 09 adolescent were found to be above average on Openness to Experiences trait whose mothers are working and 10 adolescents were found above average whose mothers are home maker.

Table 2 & 3 depicts the results of the survey conducted among Adolescent of working and non-working mothers.

Table 2 depicts the gender difference on personality traits. Female adolescent of working mothers is found to be above average on all personality traits than male adolescent whose mothers are home maker.

Table 3 depicts that female adolescent of home maker mothers are found to be above average on all personality traits than male adolescent whose mothers are home maker.

IX. CONCLUSION

As per the hypothesis No 1, the study shows, there is significant impact of maternal employment on some personality traits of college going students. As per the second hypothesis There is significant Gender difference on personality traits of college going students. Female adolescents of working mothers are above average (Mean = 5) on all personality traits compare to male adolescents (Mean=1.8). Female adolescents of home maker mothers are above average (Mean =4) on all personality traits compare to male adolescents (Mean=2.6)

X. APPLICATIONS OF THIS STUDY

This study serves as a valuable resource for educators seeking a deeper understanding of how maternal employment impacts both the academic performance and emotions of college going students. It is anticipated that the insights gained from this research will aid in the development of educational programs designed to effectively support the specific needs of all stage of adolescents with mothers in the workforce.

Moreover, mental health professionals, including counsellors and therapists working with college going students and their families, can find practical applications in this study. By offering insights into the potential effects of maternal employment on college going students' personality traits, the research may provide guidance on implementing strategies to assist college going students in navigating the unique challenges associated with their mothers' employment.

Additionally, by focusing on the aspect of work-life balance for mothers and their families, this study may serve as a catalyst for encouraging maternal employers to adopt policies that prioritize work-life balance. This, in turn, can contribute to the promotion of the well-being of maternal employees and their families, fostering a more supportive and balanced work environment.

XI. LIMITATIONS

With this smaller dataset, it might be challenging to identify subtle trends or patterns that could be more apparent in a larger study. Findings from a study is conducted in Pune may not be applicable to other regions with different socio-economic, cultural, or environmental characteristics. The study's relevance may be limited to the particular geographic context in which it is conducted. Findings from a study are conducted in late adolescents the other age criteria are not studied

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